

INTEGRATED METHODS OF LEARNING ENGLISH

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Annotation: The article covers significant points of utilizing integrated methods of learning English. On the other hand, the integrated approach is focused on providing an authentic language facilities for learners to develop listening, speaking, reading and writing skills in a meaningful context.

Key words: *pedagogy, communicative orientation, collectively-individulized interaction, hypothesis, compiling, relevant, «multilateral», mutual express.*

Integration in pedagogy involves the interaction of various elements of a system in order to obtain something holistic. Integration is considered in two aspects: as a state and as a process. Integration is intra-subject and intra-system. The form distinguishes between external and internal integration. Learning a foreign language based on an integrated approach is based on the following five principles: the communicative orientation of learning and specificity, visibility and situational speech of students and teachers in a foreign language; taking into account students experience; playful learning; comprehensive implementation of learning objectives through collectively-individulized interaction and cognitive activation of students; the use of primarily oral forms of work on the language being studied and interconnected learning.

The content of a foreign language lesson is reflected on its goals, objectives

and functions. Classes not only contribute to mental development, but also have a positive effect on the formation of the child's personality as a whole. On planning integrated English language teaching, it should be taken into account the peculiarities of the work of a primary school teacher and all the possibilities of integration, both interdisciplinary and internal. The main activity of a primary school teacher is to show, explain, train and practice. At the same time, the main activities of primary school students, especially first-graders are: perception, imitation, operating with lexical units, reproduction, ability to perform tasks according to the algorithm[1]. The main difference between learning English in 1 grade and the subsequent stages of learning is the elimination of speaking and pronunciation. Phonetics, vocabulary and grammar are served students in the relationship, rather than separately. The structure of the lesson in integrated learning is not different from the traditional structure of the lesson, however, each separate stage of the lesson is built with different types of integrations. In the course of the study it turned out that the game is an important means of achieving the goal on teaching younger students English. Participation in a role-playing game prepares the child for the fact that a foreign language is a means of communication and is used in real life situations. Integrated learning provides every child with a huge number of opportunities for self-expression: in play, work, singing songs and dances, staging plays, doing warm-ups, etc. Integration of various types and forms of activity is an effective means of achieving the goals of teaching English. In the process of integration appear sustainable[2]. The integration of training, gaming and other activities allows you to: cause sustainable motives for learning a foreign language and support them; manage the attention of trainees; to provide modeling of situations for the use of a foreign language and their variation; create favorable conditions for memorizing foreign language means; to solve important related tasks for the upbringing and development of children. Thus, the hypothesis formulated in the introduction that

the integrated teaching of English at the initial stage serves to significantly improve the effectiveness of the teaching and educational process, provided that it is implemented through the integration of accessible, familiar and interesting forms for primary school students activity, confirmed. The purpose of the study was achieved. The results of the study can be recommended for use in the practice of teaching foreign languages in elementary school, and also taken into account on compiling relevant teaching materials and textbooks.

At the present stage of the development of modern methodical thought, the basic structural unit of the educational process in a foreign language is that the lesson is seen as a complex act of communication, the main purpose and content of which is practice in solving problems of interaction between subjects of the pedagogical process, and the main way to achieve the goal and master the content serve motivated communicative tasks of varying degrees of complexity. It is generally accepted that communication in the process of teaching a foreign language can be «one-sided» and «multilateral». In the first case, we mean the organization of the educational process with the predominance of frontal forms of work, when the teacher asks, / prompts the student to speech activity — the student answers[3]. As for «multilateral» communication, for him the typical forms of work are group and collective, in which each student has the opportunity to express himself as an independent and full participant in a certain activity. It is during the organization of «multilateral» communication at the lesson of a foreign language that all the participants in the educational process interact and opportunities are created for revealing the personal potential of each student. Mutual express polls and interviews in the training group, information exchange, finding your own couple, making group decisions, coordinating joint actions, discussing «according to the rules» and other tasks allow students to practically learn a foreign language. As the experience of teaching a foreign language and the experience of numerous teachers of practice shows, it is not always possible to

organize speech interaction in a lesson using traditional methods and forms of work. The basic methodical innovations today are connected with application of interactive methods and receptions of training to a foreign language. Interactive methods are methods that allow you to learn how to interact with each other; and interactive learning, built on the interaction of all students, including the teacher. However, in the latter case the character of interaction changes: the activity of the teacher gives way to the activity of the trainees.

The essence of interactive learning is the special organization of the learning process, when all students are involved in the process of cognition. The joint activity of students in the process of mastering the teaching material means that each contributes its own individual contribution; there is an exchange of knowledge, ideas, and methods of activity. Moreover, this happens in an atmosphere of benevolence and mutual support, which allows not only receiving new knowledge, but also translates cognitive activity into higher forms of cooperation and cooperation. The objective of using interactive methods and techniques in teaching foreign languages is the social interaction of students, interpersonal communication, the most important feature of which is the ability of a person to «take the role of another», to imagine how the partner perceives it, to interpret the situation and design his own actions.

The initial function of language is to establish social purposes. In classroom, teachers are able to create an authentic facility for social interaction among learners . The prior importance is that the topics and learning activities have to be relevant and interesting to the learners. Through the use of activities the aspects of language can be implemented via integrated approach and builds new learning upon students' prior knowledge. It trains learners as individual thinkers, apt to demonstrate challenging tasks. This approach is dedicated to learn language as a process in which learners will be provided with ample opportunities to understand and practice concepts that are presented to them. Errors are treated

as part of the learner's learning process. Teachers supply a low-anxiety environment that permits learners to take risks. Corrections can be produced through modeling from teachers or peers [4]. There are many different methods that combine all aspects and mix them together in order to create integrated approach towards language learning procedure. We are aware of those methods due to the courses conducted on the subject methodology. When it comes to the communicative outcomes of learning we turn to methods of integrated approach, and what if our objective is to join the grammar into communicative language learning. So here we are supposed to look thoroughly to grammar teaching, though the majority of teaching procedure deals with the grammar in detached order. Research has shown that just teaching grammar in isolation is not an effective way of teaching language. The grammatical syllabus approach fails to provide the practical communicative aspect of learning a second language. Often times students of traditional grammar-approach classrooms believe that the things they have learned in the language classroom cannot be implemented into real life conversations.

Learning the content in meaningful context and the appropriate use of language is ignored in grammar directed methodology. Contrary to the study of grammatical rules, verbal or written communication in real situations requires the use of a wide range of language forms. When students are taught only one grammatical rule at a time, they may have difficulties in applying syntax, semantics, and pragmatics interactively . In turn, they may feel hesitation in making the choice to function in their second language. Unlike traditional teaching, which forwarded to study one single grammatical rule at a time, the integrated approach introduces grammatical rules through meaningful learning in which learners are communicating about the focal topic. Apart from this, integrated learning approach can create an authentic learning environment. The term "authentic" means applicable to real life situations. The authentic

environment is classified by the communicative nature of interactions between teacher and student, and between student and student. Students became eligible to understand what they are learning based on their prior knowledge due to these interactions. Firstly the data is presented as a whole, and then particular language skills are taught in a meaningful context. An authentic environment undertake learners in meaning making strategies depending on cooperative language learning such as group work, brainstorming, hands-on experiences, problem solving tasks, and display of visual objects. This approach does not let teachers use the students' first language for translation purposes. According to Krashen, when teachers use the primary language for translation, learners most likely will tune out the second language. In a typical composition class the teacher may write the topic on the board, and asks students if they understand the topic and then the students are left alone with the writing procedure [5]. Many students have a difficulty in developing the content of their writing assignments. This could be a result of the limited guidance from teacher and limited previous opportunities for students to practice writing for a variety of purposes.

On accordance of various reasons many students encounter writer's block in composition classes. To build an authentic environment in English classrooms means shifting the focus from memorization and routine practice to understanding and expressing creative thoughts. When introducing a new story, teachers can lead a discussion on similar experiences that have happened to the students. Vocabulary words can be incorporated through class discussion. Predictions can be made through meaningful discussions which can guide learners to a better understanding of the text. Learners are provided with opportunities to develop oral fluency in their second language through structured interaction among students, and between teachers and students. In addition to the practices that are available in the textbooks or workbooks, teachers can further develop students' verbal and written skills by asking them to re-create a new version based on what

students have learned from the literature or their interpretation of the text. Students are obliged to present their new version to the class. The re-construction can take place in many forms such as skit, poem, story, letter, biography, picture with illustrations, etc. The product display not only that student's percept the story, but also that, they have the aptness to take what they have learned and apply it in a new context. This example depicts the authentic learning environment that can help second-language learners to develop language skills in a balanced manner. The significance of teachers' presence in creating an authentic learning environment that is appropriate and interesting to the learners is very high. In contrast to the typical idea of treating learners as blank slates, the integrative approach offers that teachers allow students to investigate and generate new knowledge during the learning procedure. This can be fulfilled via interactive learning environment. It is specified by divergent questioning techniques, authentic problem solving tasks, and learners' verbal and written sharing of thoughts. When learners have successful experiences in conveying their ideas for themselves, they have not only accomplished the communicative function, but also gained confidence in the usage of second language.

References

1. Иброхимова, Л. И. Interactive methods of teaching in English lessons / Л. И. Иброхимова. — Текст : непосредственный // Молодой ученый. — 2017. — № 47 (181). — С. 203-205. — URL: <https://moluch.ru/archive/181/46476/> (дата обращения: 06.01.2023).
2. Concept of development of foreign language education of the Republic of Kazakhstan. – Almaty, 2006.
3. Sysoev P. V. Language multicultural education: what is it? // Foreign languages at school. – № 4.-2-14p

4. Gorlova N. Ah. Personality-activity method of teaching foreign languages to younger schoolchildren.M.: Moscow state pedagogical University,2010.- 248
5. Alekseeva T. L. Experimental teaching of English in kindergarten // Foreign languages at school – 1989. – № 5. 9-10 p